

Consent Form

“Productivity & Wellbeing in the Workplace”

Principal Investigator

anonymized

Collaborators

anonymized

Purpose

The modern workplace demands more of its employees than ever before as technology assumes a larger role. Workers are asked to perform a broad variety of complex tasks, working in a global and fast-paced environment, and experiencing interruptions and distractions. In this context, the productivity and well-being of the individual as well as the team and the overall organizations is increasingly important, yet little is known about them and their relation. The broader vision of this research is to better understand productivity and well-being on an individual and team level, and to develop approaches that support professionals in spending their time well at work.

Study Procedure and Collected Data (also see figure below)

Overall, this study runs for 6 to 8 weeks and consists of the following steps:

An **introduction** in which we will explain the study and its structure to you, ask you about your preferences for work time, self-reports and survey timing, as well as ask you to fill in a preliminary survey on demographics that will take **no more than 30 minutes**.

Hourly Self-reports (prompt on smart watch). Through the course of this study, you will be asked to wear a smart watch, e.g. Apple Watch or Samsung Watch, that we will provide, and you will be asked to respond to regular questionnaires on the device. These self-reports will be prompted at regular intervals (e.g. each hour) throughout the workday and will take **about 1 minute** to fill out. You can adjust the notification hours as needed and have the option to postpone or omit self-reports at any point in time.

End of Day Reflection (online survey). To complement the self-reports with more thorough reflections, you will be asked to fill out a short (**approximately 5-minute**) **questionnaire at the end of each day**. The questionnaires will provide a summary of your self-reports for the day and/or week and ask you to reflect about your work, experiences at work, productivity, and well-being in more depth.

Follow-up Interviews (online or in person). We will interview you at the end of the study to better understand your experiences in the study. The interviews will be audio recorded (if you consent) and should take **no longer than 30minutes**.

Benefits

As a token of our appreciation, you will get to keep the provided smart watch after the study and you will have the chance to learn more about your perception of individual and team productivity, work impediments and behavior, and your personality. By participating in this study, you are contributing to an ongoing effort to improve the future of the workplace. In the long term, you may benefit from better productivity tools, because the results of this study will be used to inform the design of software to better support productivity and well-being in the workplace.

Risks

The main risk is the loss of time required to participate in the study. You may experience frustration if the self-report notifications come at inappropriate times, potentially disrupting important work or interrupting a meeting. To mitigate the disturbance factor of the notifications, we will collect your notification preferences prior to running the study. You can also adjust the notification start time, end time, and frequency through the app settings at any time, and have the option to postpone or skip all notifications. Furthermore, you are free to withdraw from participation at any point during the study, without the need to provide a reason.

Data Storage, Confidentiality & Retention

The **survey data** will be stored in the online survey tool hosted at the <university name> and only the involved researchers will have access to this data. The watch will only be used to record **self-reports**. We will not collect any other information, such as location information, from the watch for this study.

All data will be treated confidentially and only reside on machines of the university researchers in <country>. Your data will be used and seen only by researchers directly involved with this project. After the entire data collection, the self-reports, surveys, and interviews will be coded and analyzed by the research team. In any case, raw data may not be stored for longer than one year. All identifying information will be kept strictly separate at all times from any other collected data and will be stored in a different location at the <university name>. Only the involved researchers will have access to this information. Furthermore, it will not be associated with the data after it has been analyzed. After the study is finished, your identifying information will be permanently deleted. The anonymized, non-identifiable data produced from the study will be stored for five years, after which it will be permanently and irrevocably deleted. No identifiable responses will ever be shared with your team, managers, or the Company.

Uses of the Study Data

For our research, we will only use your anonymized data, use pseudonyms to refer to participants that cannot be traced back to you, and no direct or indirect identifying information will ever be shared outside of the research group and the confines of this study without your explicit permission. The results of this study will appear in a thesis written at the <university name>. Additionally, the study will be published in a research paper and may potentially appear in both internal and external academic research presentations and publications, such as academic journals and conference proceedings.

Contact for Information about the Study

If you have any questions or desire further information with respect to the study, please contact <PI Name and Email>.

Consent for Study Participation

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You are free to withdraw your participation at any point during the study, without giving any reason and without any negative consequence and by simply sending one of the listed researchers an email. Any information you contribute up to your withdrawal will be retained and used in an anonymous form in this study unless you request not to retain and use the data.

With your check mark you confirm the following statements:

- I understand the goal and procedures of the study and the applicable conditions.
- I had the opportunity to ask questions. I understood the answers and accept them.
- I am at least 18 years old.
- I had enough time to make the decision to participate and I agree to the participation.

In no way does this waive your legal rights or release the investigators or involved institutions from their legal or professional responsibilities.